

Balancing Instructional Modes using PAT Maths Data: Analysis at SCOTS PGC College

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Abstract

At SCOTS PGC College, we have partnered with Maths Pathway since 2017, in order to target each student at their point of need. We have found this differentiated approach to be of benefit to students both consolidating and excelling academically. In this analysis, we aim to further the work of Steinbergs & Smith (2024) which examined PAT Maths and Maths Pathway data in a Victorian school, finding correlations between Maths Pathway usage and students' PAT Maths attainment and growth. We find that SCOTS PGC College data exhibits similar trends, with students attaining approximately 1.60 years' growth per year as measured by PAT Maths. Maths Pathway has a minimum recommended dosage of 52 modules completed per year; we find that students meeting or exceeding this threshold clearly outperform their peers on PAT Maths. It may be that these findings are of use to other schools looking to lift outcomes, implementing dosage targets that are supported by data.

Keywords: eLearning, mathematics, personalisation, mastery learning, differentiation, dosage, modules

Background

The School Context

SCOTS PGC College is located in Warwick, Queensland, and has been educating students for over 100 years. The College is a Prep to Year 12 day and boarding school located in a predominantly agricultural area. Students from Prep to Year 6 are chiefly day students, while approximately one third of the student population are boarders from Year 7 to 12. The College is a single stream school to Year 5, two streams in Year 6 and three streams from Year 7 to 12. At

Year 7 there is a large intake of students transferring from local primary schools, rural and remote schools and students who have been learning via distance education.

Version 9.0 of the Australian Curriculum underpins teaching, learning and assessment across Years Prep to 10. Then, in Year 10, students choose one of two Senior School pathways tailored toward their unique life goals - UniWay and WorkWay. Mathematics courses in the senior years are based on general and applied courses developed by the Queensland Curriculum and Assessment Authority (QCAA). SCOTS PGC College is committed to helping students find their learning pathway to develop areas of passion and help students reach their potential.

Differentiation with Maths Pathway

At SCOTS PGC College, our experience reflected the findings of Australian research which indicated that “in any given year level, there is a five- to six-year difference between the most advanced and the least advanced ten percent of students”, with certain studies indicating that this gap can extend to as much as eight years in mathematics (Goss & Hunter, 2015). For a Year 7 cohort at the start of a given year, the gaps between the highest achieving and lowest achieving students’ capabilities in Mathematics appeared to be at least seven years. Some students were still developing foundational understandings of material from Year 2, while others were comfortably engaging with material at a Year 9 or 10 level.

This variability in student levels caused difficulties meeting the needs of a class of diverse students. SCOTS PGC College initiated a partnership with Maths Pathway in 2017 to focus on differentiated instruction that addresses students' individual competencies and areas for improvement, promotes mastery, and enables all learners to progress along a continuum from

their current level of understanding. This initiative is implemented across Years 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10.

Maths Pathway is “a sustainable, evidence-based programmatic approach to maximised teacher efficacy in delivering differentiated maths learning for students across Australia ... Critical to Maths Pathway’s success is the pedagogical model that empowers teachers to use assessments and evidence based pedagogical strategies effectively and efficiently.” (Sundar & Schenke, 2021).

While the implementation of Maths Pathway incorporates some technological elements, it is not merely an adjunct to traditional instruction. Our teaching teams continue to base the core of their instruction, their course planning, their assessment and their reporting in this model. They have established something cohesive and end-to-end that consistently targets each student's specific needs.

The Basis for this Analysis

School-level Data Observed so Far

Staff observations are that the Maths Pathway teaching and learning model has allowed students to build knowledge from their unique point of need, even allowing some students to experience success in Mathematics for the first time. Different learning rates have allowed some students to spend time in an area to develop mastery, while others have progressed to content beyond their year-level, and especially capable students have completed Year 10 content and started senior Mathematics courses early.

PAT Maths data has been analysed to identify common areas of need across different year levels in order to target energiser activities (start of lesson activities). For example, in Year 7

operations with fractions was identified as an area needing consolidation in many students, and so energiser activities were selected to focus on this area.

We are interested in investigating further improvements to our teaching approach using multiple data sources, specifically: PAT Maths growth, PAT Maths attainment, and Maths Pathway module dosage. Of particular interest is the balance we currently strike between whole-class teaching of explicit topics and individually differentiated student work.

PAT Maths Data Collection

The Progressive Achievement Test for Mathematics (PAT Maths) is provided by the Australian Council for Education Research (ACER). PAT Maths aims to measure "...what students in Foundation to Year 10 know, understand and are capable of across domains, and help monitor progress over time." (ACER, n.d.). Our students take this test annually early in Term One of the school year (January or February), delivered through ACER's online testing platform.

Maths Pathway Dosage Data Collection

Through Maths Pathway's online platform, students' 'dosage' is recorded year to year. This is a count of the number of 'modules' a student completed during each academic year, with each module typically taking around 30 minutes to complete. This dosage data indicates the extent to which the program was used by an individual student. Maths Pathway provides our school with a guideline recommendation of at least 52 modules completed per year as being an effective dosage level.

It could be considered that 'dosage' is a proxy for the balance of time spent on whole-class instruction vs. individualised, differentiated work. A relationship between 'dosage'

and PAT Maths results could be of use to faculties trying to determine that balance they strike in their own classrooms.

Comparable analysis

We note that this analysis builds upon the work of Steinbergs & Smith (2024) in a Victorian school. In that analysis, “[...] students appeared to grow at 142% of the Australian norm, as measured by PAT Maths (approximately 1.4 years’ learning per year). [...] Moreover, the level of use of Maths Pathway appears to be directly associated with that strong performance.”

Key Research Questions

Drawing upon PAT Maths test data and Maths Pathway dosage data, in this analysis, we aim to explore:

- (a) how our students’ growth over time compares to Australian norms, as measured by PAT Maths data; and
- (b) how PAT Maths data differs between students who have met or exceeded the minimum recommended dosage level (52 modules per year) compared with their peers who have not met that threshold.

Data Sets

Students with PAT Maths Growth Results

PAT Maths results from 2022, 2023, and 2024 were considered. We looked specifically at results from Year 7 in 2022 and 2023; and then correspondingly from Year 8 in 2023 and 2024.

Due to some changes in enrolments and some absences on the day of the test, not all data points from Year 7 assessments matched with Year 8 assessments. Only data that matched across both time points was considered so growth across that period could be examined. This captured the large majority of students in these cohorts; the only students excluded were those without PAT Maths data available due to absence and/or students who were not enrolled at SCOTS PGC College for the relevant time period.

Students with Year 8 PAT Maths data and relevant Maths Pathway dosage data

Maths Pathway dosage data from 2022 and 2023 was considered. Students who were not enrolled at SCOTS PGC College during either of those years would not have any dosage data available. In this analysis, we were interested in Year 8 PAT Maths performance (a test common to all students in the data set), so looked at the dosage leading up to that test. That is, during the year prior to a student sitting their January or February Year 8 assessment.

With no unique identifiers common to both data sources, PAT Maths data and Maths Pathway dosage data were matched using students' names. In this data set, there was only one pair of students with the same first and last names, so they were excluded from the analysis to remove any risk of ambiguity. The matched data was used for all analyses. The resulting data set pertained to 95 students, of which 52 were in Year 7 in 2022 and 43 were in Year 7 in 2023. This captured the large majority of students in these cohorts.

Analysis and Results

Student Growth from Year to Year

The results of each PAT Maths test include a 'PAT scale score' for each student. This is effectively a Rasch scale used across each year's assessment. "Scale scores are measured on an interval scale. This means that a difference of 5 in scale scores in the middle of the PAT scale (for example, from 50 to 55) is equivalent to the same difference on any other part of the scale (for example, from 15 to 20 or from 85 to 90)." This allows students' growth to be measured over time (ACER, 2011).

Australian norms show that the Year 7 students are expected to average a PAT scale score of 131.6; and Year 8 students 133.6 (ACER, 2022). This means the typical growth expected between Year 7 and Year 8 is approximately 2.0 points on the PAT scale. This gives a benchmark that can be used to see whether students are making at least 1 year's growth per year - by growing by at least 2.0 points on the PAT Maths scale from their Year 7 assessment to their Year 8 assessment.

Examining students' average attainment on Year 7 and 8 PAT Maths, the average growth shown in our data set is 3.2 points on the PAT scale. This is substantially higher than the 2.0 benchmark (approximately 60% higher), as pictured in Figure 1. If we take 2.0 points to represent 1 year's growth, then we would estimate that our students were making 1.60 years' growth each year.

Figure 1

Average increase over 1 year (7 to 8)

Figure 1: Typical annual growth between Year 7 and Year 8 as measured by PAT Maths against Australian norms (ACER, 2022), compared with the measured average PAT Maths growth between Year 7 and Year 8 at SCOTS PGC College N = 95 students. This indicates that SCOTS PGC College students are on average growing in mathematical attainment by approximately 1.60 years per academic year.

These results appear very strong. It seems likely that using Maths Pathway contributed to achieving this success - since it is embedded so deeply into teachers' practice day to day.

Student PAT Maths Performance and Maths Pathway Dosage

We consider student performance in Year 8 PAT Maths. This test is common to all 95 students in the data set, with 52 sitting the test in 2023 and 43 in 2024. For each student, we

consider their PAT scale score. We compare this against their Maths Pathway dosage in the lead-up to that test - that is, the total number of modules completed in Year 8 for those students.

Maths Pathway has a guideline for a minimum effective dosage of 52 modules per year. This is equivalent to an average of 4 modules completed per Topic Test across 13 Units in the year. We find that of the 95 students in the data set, 55 (58%) met or exceeded this requirement. Comparing this “high dosage” group against the other students we see a noticeable difference in Year 8 PAT Maths attainment.

A potential caveat is that these cohorts of students do include some with specific, additional learning needs. No exclusions of specific students have been made for the sake of statistical power, so it is possible that these students would be overrepresented in the “low dosage” group and might contribute to the difference in PAT Maths attainments between the two groups. However, given that the low dosage group was 42% of the whole set and that the median - rather than the mean - has been the central focus, they aren't dominating the effect.

This data set appears to show a higher level of Year 8 PAT Maths attainment for the subset of students who met or exceeded the dosage target of 52 modules per year.

Figure 2

Figure 2: Median PAT scaled score on Year 8 PAT Maths in 2022 and 2023 at SCOTS PGC College N = 95 students. Students are separated into two groups, based on whether they met Maths Pathway's recommended minimum dosage (at least 52 modules completed per year) in the year of their Year 8 PAT assessment. On average, students' PAT Maths scale scores increase by 2.0 points nationally from Year 7 to Year 8, indicating a difference of 2.0 points as a reasonable measure for about a year's growth in PAT Maths. The high dosage group is almost two years (3.9 points) ahead of the low dosage group.

Conclusion

In the context of SCOTS PGC College's implementation of Maths Pathway, we set out to explore (a) whether our students were growing rapidly in maths attainment from year to year; and (b) whether students who met or exceeded the minimum recommended dosage level of 52 modules per year had stronger outcomes than their peers.

Data for 95 middle school students from 2022 to 2024 showed that our students appeared to grow at 160% of the Australian norm, as measured by PAT Maths (approximately 1.60 years'

learning per year). Students whose use of the learning tool was higher - those whose dosage exceeded 52 modules per year - showed stronger performance on Year 8 PAT Maths than those with a lower dosage. 58% of students met or exceeded this dosage threshold; and had median growth in attainment from Year 7 to Year 8 well above that which is typical.

These results are consistent with strong PAT Maths attainment and growth for students using Maths Pathway, particularly when their usage meets or exceeds the recommended threshold of 52 modules per unit. This was consistent with the findings of Steinbergs & Smith (2024) within a Victorian school.

These findings may have implications within our school and in other schools as well. It may be that teaching teams want to target some percentage of students meeting or exceeding that threshold. In our school this would likely mean deliberately planning how teachers balance time spent in the classroom, providing whole-class teaching aimed at common exposure; in addition to personalised differentiated learning aimed at deep mastery. Having a concrete target for the latter can help inform planning around the former.

Overall, this analysis supports that there is rapid student learning at SCOTS PGC College while implementing Maths Pathway. Drawing upon PAT Maths data allows our teaching team to consider what goals and expectations to set for students, while also giving confidence that the formative observations of our teaching staff appear to be correct - that, working with Maths Pathway and focussing on differentiation, we are having a substantial and meaningful impact on student learning and outcomes.

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